

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING PERIPHERAL INTRAVENOUS CATHETER INSERTION COMPETENCY OF
HOME HEALTH NURSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Purpose/Objectives: To develop, implement, and evaluate a peripheral intravenous catheter (PIVC) competency training program for home health infusion registered nurses (RNs).

Background: As PIVC insertion knowledge and skill remains fundamental for RNs, home health nurses are frequently required to establish intravenous access. According to the 2013 Infusion Nurses Society, up to 57% of nursing students receive PIVC training, while many current staff RNs report a lack of PIVC education during their clinical setting orientation (Glover et al., 2017), therefore leading to lower levels of PIVC competence. **Methodology:** Establishing a policy requiring all RNs entering the home health organization to undergo a PIVC training program, and their PIVC knowledge and skills competence evaluated. The evidence-based practice (EBP) PIVC training program included: (a) online video and in-person/hands-on training, (b) a pre- and post-implementation knowledge questionnaire, (c) a PIVC skills checklist, and (d) evaluation of the training program. All RNs employed during the project implementation were invited to participate. **Results:** Pre- and Post-PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment scores were explored. There was a total count change score of 1 and an average count change score of 0.33. RNs were assessed using a PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist. Three of the 28 checklist items were completed by less than 100% of the RNs. Lastly, the RNs were given two insertion attempts to be assessed, and with the overall second attempt scores, there was a total change score of 32% and an average percentage change score of 10.67.

Keywords: peripheral intravenous catheter, IV, intravenous catheter, insertion, registered nurses, RNs, nurses, home health, home care, infusion nursing, infusion therapy, training program, training, competency

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND	1
Significance.....	2
Purpose.....	3
Framework	3
Star Point 1: Discovery Research	5
Star Point 2: Evidence Summary	5
Star Point 3: Translation to Guidelines	6
Star Point 4: Practice Integration	6
Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Search Strategies.....	8
Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Issues.....	9
Evidence-Based Practice Training Programs.....	9
Nursing Skills Competence.....	11
Synthesis	12
Summary.....	13
METHODS	15
Study Design.....	15
Setting and Sample	15
Ethical Considerations	15
Procedure	16
Star Point 1: Discovery Research	16
Star Point 2: Evidence Summary	16
Star Point 3: Translation to Guidelines	16
Star Point 4: Practice Integration	18
Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation	20
RESULTS	22

RN Demographics.....	22
PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores	22
RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items	23
Percentage of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Completed.....	25
DISCUSSION	26
Limitations	27
Future Implications	28
REFERENCES	29
APPENDIX A: Consent to Use the Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation	33
APPENDIX B: Project Timeline	36
APPENDIX C: Consent of Use the PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Tool	37
APPENDIX D: PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Tool.....	38
APPENDIX E: Consent to Use the Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Skills Checklist	39
APPENDIX F: Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Skills Checklist.....	40
APPENDIX G: Participation Consent Form Letter	41
APPENDIX H: Didactic Training Material.....	42
APPENDIX I: Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Placement Policy.....	43

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Demographics	22
2. PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores	23
3. RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items	24
4. Percentage of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Completed.....	25

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation	4
2. Modified Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation.....	7

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Ephesians 3:20

Background

Many essential medical treatments require intravenous (IV) access to sustain or save lives. IV access allows a patient to receive these treatments, especially in emergent situations. Although IV access devices are ubiquitous across healthcare settings, insertion skills vary amongst providers. Many patients experience peripheral IV catheter (PIVC) insertion as a painful procedure that causes suffering. Attempts at insertion are highly related to the skill level of the practicing registered nurse (RN) and depend on the healthcare professional's training and expertise (Schuster et al., 2016b).

Failure to insert PIVCs on the first attempt contributes to significant deleterious sequelae. Sixty-nine percent of PIVCs fail and require premature removal due to phlebitis, infection, leakage, infiltration, occlusion, and dislodgement (Glover et al., 2017; Keleekai et al., 2016; Parreira et al., 2019). These iatrogenic outcomes may result from the insertion technique of the healthcare worker (Glover et al., 2017; Parreira et al., 2019). Patients may become dissatisfied with care (Galang et al., 2019) and may also experience lengthier hospitalizations (Parreira et al., 2019) when their PIVC therapy is complicated. Additionally, costs of insertions further distress healthcare organizations. According to Keleekai et al. (2016), one PIVC insertion may cost between \$28 - \$35. Nationally, however, premature PIVC removals cost \$1.5 billion per year (Keleekai et al., 2016) and globally, can reach up to \$17.5 billion per year (Glover et al., 2017). Nevertheless, these PIVC costs and adverse patient care may be improved.

The education of RNs related to PIVC insertion is one approach to mitigating the adverse sequela associated with unsuccessful PIVC placement. Schuster et al. (2016b) found that RNs within an acute care setting had insufficient education and training opportunities related to PIVC insertion skills. Keleekai et al. (2016) noted the first PIVC insertion attempt might be associated

with the healthcare professionals' knowledge, skill, and confidence with PIVCs. A deficit in a healthcare professional's knowledge and skill may result in inadequate "...patient assessment, selection of inappropriate intravenous catheter and insertion site, short dwell time, and poor complication identification and treatment" (Schuster et al., 2016b, p. 159). As evidence suggests, additional PIVC education is necessary for RNs, and although there is a robust amount of research indicating PIVC training in acute care settings is suboptimal, this author was unable to identify evidence specific to PIVC training in home health settings.

Significance

The use of home health care is advantageous for health care systems, patient outcomes and continuity of care. According to HomeCare (2017), "patients who receive home health care after a hospital discharge save the system about \$6500 over the course of a year" (para. 1), while still generating a greater access for care, especially in patients who have limited resources (Landers, 2010). Furthermore, patient outcomes rise as home health care decreases readmissions and death and provides patient care in a setting in which they prefer to be seen (HomeCare, 2017).

As a vast population of patients are cared for at home, home health RNs are frequently required to establish IV access. However, many home health organizations lack PIVC training programs related to RN PIVC competency. According to Nickel (2019), a competent nurse is knowledgeable and skillful in safely practicing a segment of care. At a home health organization in Orange County, California, PIVC training was not provided during orientation for newly hired RNs, yet PIVC insertion competency remains a fundamental skill for RNs. According to the 2013 Infusion Nurses Society, approximately 57% of nursing students receive PIVC training. In contrast, many current staff RNs report a lack of PIVC education during their clinical setting

orientation (Glover et al., 2017), which may lead to lower levels of PIVC insertion competence. A PIVC training program is needed for home health organizations, which offer intravenous services, to improve home health RNs' PIVC insertion competencies.

Purpose

Therefore, the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a PIVC insertion training program for home health infusion RNs. The objectives were to:

1. Develop and pilot a PIVC placement policy and training program
2. Pilot the PIVC skills program over a two-month period
3. Evaluate and modify the PIVC program based on project results

Framework

The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation was developed in 2004 by Dr. Kathleen R. Stevens (The University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio [UT Health San Antonio], 2015). It presents a simple framework to encourage the translation of evidence into practice (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). The model identifies the cycles of knowledge transformation by moving discoveries into operation (UT Health San Antonio, 2015).

Knowledge transformation is the application of research into care by incorporating information through phases. The foundations of knowledge transformation include the need for research to form clinical decisions, the need for experience and theoretical principles, and the need to develop and evaluate organizational recommendations (UT Health San Antonio, 2015).

Ultimately, the goal of knowledge transformation is to improve healthcare quality (Stevens, 2013).

The model provides stages that encompass a vast amount of research but allows a clinician to condense the knowledge into a modest summation. The five-point star model embodies essential phases of knowledge transformation: discovery research (evidence search), evidence summary (also referred to as a synthesis), translation to guidelines (creation of a plan), practice integration (the project), and process, outcome evaluation (UT Health San Antonio, 2015; see Figure 1).

Figure 1

The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation has proven successful in various evidence-based practice (EBP) projects. This model has guided curriculum changes at nursing

schools by increasing nursing faculty's and Master of Science in Nursing students' competency in EBP (Kesten et al. 2019; Orta et al., 2016). As various projects have found success utilizing this model, it was also suitable for the author's DNP project of implementing a PIVC skills training program into a home health organization. The model allowed the author to research and summarize the knowledge needed to develop an EBP PIVC skills training program. Furthermore, the model also permitted the author to incorporate and modify policies and implement the newly developed EBP PIVC skills training program into a home health organization.

Star Point 1: Discovery Research

Discovery research is the first stage of knowledge transformation. New information is discovered through investigation, which becomes the foundation for clinical decisions (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). The author conducted a literature review using key words, "home health," "home care," "intravenous catheter," "infusion therapy," "nurses," and "training." The author then critiqued the research and noted if the study was valuable to develop the PIVC skills training program (see Figure 2).

Star Point 2: Evidence Summary

Evidence summary is the task of synthesizing research into a statement. This stage generates new knowledge through the summarization of information. By synthesizing the studies, reliability increases (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). Additionally, this stage has its advantages, which include combining multiple research findings into a more straightforward form, generalizing the information, and reducing bias (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). After conducting a literature review and creating a Table of Evidence, reviewed studies were graded on their design and applicability within a home health setting using levels of evidence. Then, the

author synthesized the various studies' knowledge into a systematic literature review that is presented in the Review of the Literature section (see Figure 2).

Star Point 3: Translation to Guidelines

Translation into guidelines provides summarized information to shareholders and considers time and costs suitable for the organization (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). Also called clinical practice guidelines, the evidence may be formed into protocols and clinical pathways (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). Strongly developed guidelines are reproducible and specific to the population and setting (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). Rather than creating a guideline, however, the author developed a PIVC skills training program to institute within a home health organization. This program included a policy and procedures to teach and evaluate RN PIVC competency (see Figure 2).

Star Point 4: Practice Integration

Practice integration is vital. The latest knowledge is required by health care to ensure best practices are provided by first uncovering evidence and then applying the evidence into guidelines. This next step necessitates changes by the organization and clinicians (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). The author piloted and integrated the EBP PIVC program into a home health organization (see Figure 2).

Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation

Evaluation is the last stage of the knowledge transformation model. The impact of the new EBP is evaluated by considering clinician and client satisfaction, efficiency, client outcomes, and financial implications (UT Health San Antonio, 2015). After the implementation of the PIVC program, the author evaluated the piloted practice change for feasibility, practicality,

and clinician satisfaction. This stage allowed the author to create modifications to improve the program (see Figure 2). Quality EBP implementation was lastly formed and finalized.

Figure 2

Modified Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation – PIVC Skills Training

Review of Literature

Search Strategies

In this section, the literature was reviewed to support this project. The following databases were used to conduct a literature search: PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane Library. The search terms used were “peripheral intravenous catheter,” “peripheral intravenous access,” “intravenous catheter insertion,” “intravenous access,” “infusion therapy,” “nurses,” “home health,” “home care,” and “training.” The search was limited to research studies published in the English language from 2010 to April 2020. A manual search of the reference lists from the identified articles supplemented the electronic literature search. Articles reviewed included studies examining the adult population, nurses, student nurses, and hospital/acute care settings. Articles excluded from the review of literature studied the pediatric population, ultrasound-guided IV insertion, and central venous access. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria of the literature, the author reviewed eight articles.

The purpose of this DNP project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a PIVC skills insertion training program for home health infusion RNs. Since the project was to develop an RN PIVC insertion training program, the literature review focused on issues surrounding PIVCs, EBP training programs, and nursing skills competence. Furthermore, the author aimed to establish a training program within a home care setting; however, the studies identified and reviewed were conducted in acute care settings, and no study was conducted in home health. This literature search identified a significant gap in knowledge requiring the need for further research of PIVCs in home care settings.

Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Issues

PIVCs are the most common, invasive procedures performed by healthcare professionals and are essential for providing timely care and intravenous medications (Galang et al., 2019; Garner et al., 2018). Roughly a billion of PIVCs are inserted annually (Carr et al., 2017). Within acute care settings, 80% of patients receive IV therapy (Souza-Junior et al., 2020).

Though PIVCs are standard procedures, they are also a source of iatrogenic outcomes, and inadequately trained nurses may instantaneously negatively affect patients (Souza-Junior et al., 2020). A successful PIVC insertion is indicated as a catheter placed within a vein shown by a flashback of blood (Keleekai et al., 2016). A failed PIVC, however, is a premature catheter removal or an improper insertion (Carr et al., 2017; Parreira et al., 2019). Failed PIVCs may result from inadequate insertion techniques, infection, dislodgement, and other complications (Carr et al., 2017; Galang et al., 2019; Parreira et al., 2019). Improper PIVC insertions are under-recognized experiences (Carr et al., 2017). Rates for failed PIVCs range from 33% to 69% (Galang et al., 2019). Additionally, failed PIVCs may also create distress among patients and increase their hospital stay as complications, such as infections, may have occurred (Galang et al., 2019; Parreira et al., 2019).

Evidence-Based Practice Training Programs

As PIVCs are essential in health care, RNs should be thoroughly trained in insertion techniques. Many nurses do not obtain the skill to insert a PIVC until they have begun their careers and learn this skill from seasoned nurses (Garner et al., 2018). Many nurses, however, are not experts in vascular access (Keleekai et al., 2016). Furthermore, RNs who are inexperienced with PIVC insertions may cause patients discomfort, prevent timely treatment, and increase the use of supplies and costs (Lyons & Kasker, 2012). As nurses do not receive an ample amount of

PIVC education or training, continuing instruction is warranted to ensure proper skill competency (Garner et al., 2018; Keleekai et al., 2016).

Various studies examined PIVC training programs among nurses and nursing students. Multiple studies included simulation within their training programs (Garner et al., 2018; İsmailoğlu & Zaybak, 2018; Keleekai et al., 2016; Lyons & Kasker, 2012; Souza-Junior et al., 2020). Simulation is an interactive way of learning that allows a person to experience situations through a modeled or virtual experience (İsmailoğlu & Zaybak, 2018). Garner et al. (2018) utilized a hands-on, low-fidelity simulation, which is the use of mannequins or task trainers to practice a specific skill. This technique differs from the virtual reality (VR) simulation, which is an interactive, computer-based technology, incorporated by İsmailoğlu and Zaybak (2018). Although Keleekai et al. (2016) implemented hands-on and virtually simulated methods, the authors also emphasized the value of incorporating blended learning styles to meet the various ways in which one best understands information. To ensure blended learning, Keleekai et al. (2016) employed three simulation tools and further included a two hour PIVC online course and an eight hour live training workshop within their program. Just as Keleekai et al. (2016) valued learning styles, Lyon and Kasker (2012) found the significance of the differing ways of teaching information as well, and implementing adult learning standards to guide their training program. The adult learning standards are the following: adults need to be self-directed, adults learn from experience, adults use problem-solving approaches, and adults need to know the learned information is useful (Lyons & Kasker, 2012). The adult learning standards were incorporated through didactic PIVC material and simulations using computer haptic devices and mannequins (Lyons & Kasker, 2012).

Incorporating PIVC skills training programs proved successful among nurses and nursing students. Through their continuing education PIVC training programs, nurses significantly increased their skill level (Garner et al., 2018; İsmailoğlu & Zaybak, 2018; Keleekai et al., 2016; Lyons & Kasker, 2012). Although Garner et al. (2018), İsmailoğlu & Zaybak (2018), Keleekai et al. (2016), and Lyons and Kasker (2012) all noted the RNs improving their skill level, Keleekai et al. (2016) indicated the decrease of insertion attempts also signified an increase of PIVC insertion skill. Additionally, Lyons and Kasker (2012) also supported their measuring of skill by incorporating the Infusion Nurses Society (INS) guidelines of PIVC insertion competency. Furthermore, Garner et al. (2018), Keleekai et al. (2016), and Lyons and Kasker (2012) noted an increase in PIVC knowledge among their participating nurses after undergoing the researchers' training interventions. A differentiation between the studies conducted by Keleekai et al. (2016), Lyons and Kasker (2012), and the other studies reviewed, however, was the use of various teaching techniques, which included both online and simulation trainings. It is imperative to note, however, that though these tactics were a success, developing the skill of properly inserting a PIVC is complex and dependent on the learner's interest and motivation, as well as their stage in their nursing career (Souza-Junior et al., 2020).

Nursing Skills Competence

As PIVCs are essential in-patient care, nurses need to be competent in proper PIVC insertion. According to Lyons and Kasker (2012), experienced RNs state a lack of confidence inserting PIVCs through training with phlebotomists and IV teams. PIVC skills competence may include IV and catheter selection, insertion, securement, dwell time, and complication identification (Keleekai et al., 2016). Additionally, a successful PIVC insertion on the first attempt may also indicate a clinician's PIVC competence (Carr et al., 2017; Keleekai et al.,

2016). Although the rate for first-time PIVC insertion success is broad, ranging from 18% to 98% (Carr et al., 2017), Keleekai et al. (2016) found that a clinician may require 2.18 to 2.35 attempts to establish a PIVC. To combat multiple PIVC insertion attempts and patient complications, the healthcare professional must be knowledgeable of IV anatomy and assessment, confident, and skillful in PIVC access (Keleekai et al., 2016). Furthermore, Carr et al. (2017) state that a certification, experience, and self-reported skill level contribute to successful PIVC insertions. Lastly, healthcare organizations must also be held accountable to their employees for providing quality care. It is essential for healthcare organizations to offer EBP recommendations and protocols for their healthcare professionals to ensure proper PIVC insertion (Garner et al., 2018; Parreira et al., 2019).

Synthesis

The author reviewed eight studies. Of these, three studies were random control trials (RCTs), one study was a mixed-methods systematic review of literature, one study was an integrative, mixed-methods literature review, one study was a prospective observational study, one study was a one-way repeated measures design (Lyons & Kasker, 2012), and one study was descriptive. Using Polit and Beck's (2008) levels of evidence, the RCTs were graded level II, Carr et al. (2017) was graded level III, Lyons and Kasker (2012) and Parreira et al. (2019) were graded level IV, Souza-Junior et al. (2020) was graded level V, and lastly, Garner et al. (2018) was graded level VI.

The three RCT studies were conducted by Galang et al. (2019), İsmailoğlu and Zaybak (2018), and Keleekai et al. (2016). Galang et al. (2019) studied outcomes of various types of PIVCs. İsmailoğlu and Zaybak (2018) compared the use of a virtual simulator and a plastic arm on PIVC insertion skill. Lastly, Keleekai et al. (2016) compared RNs' PIVC knowledge,

confidence, and skill with and without a PIVC blended learning training program. The systematic review of literature conducted by Carr et al. (2017) studied “tools, clinical prediction rules, and algorithms” (p. 851) of PIVCs. The review included 13 English language studies published between 2005 to 2017 from various countries. The objective of the review was to determine what factors could determine PIVC insertion success. Visible or palpable veins and clinicians who deemed the insertion would be successful or have experience with numerous PIVC insertions were the factors found to increase successful PIVC insertions (Carr et al., 2017). The review, however, could not detail recommendations, such as utilizing a vascular expert, to increase insertion success (Carr et al., 2017). Lastly, the integrative, mixed methods literature review conducted by Souza-Junior et al. (2020) evaluated 24 studies published between 2011 to 2017. The objective of the review was to determine strategies that best educate nursing students on PIVC insertion (Souza-Junior et al., 2020). Souza-Junior et al. (2020) concluded that one specific strategy to teach PIVC insertion was inconclusive, however, by combining theoretical material with a virtual simulation or mannequin, produced the best outcomes.

Summary

In summary, PIVCs are common within patient care and RNs must be appropriately trained to establish IV access. Failed PIVCs may contribute to patient complications. To combat subsequent issues that may arise from failed PIVCs, healthcare organizations must provide RNs PIVC training. Literature suggests that both hands-on and virtual simulations were successful in PIVC training programs. Through PIVC training programs, evidence noted that nurses and nursing students increased their skills and knowledge of PIVCs. Therefore, the literature provided evidence for the author to incorporate both an online and a live, hands-on simulation, PIVC training program. Considering that research provides evidence of PIVC training programs

in acute care settings, little research is known of PIVC training programs within home care settings. Thus, an online and in-person simulation training program took place within a home health organization.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a PIVC insertion skills competency training program for home health infusion RNs. The objectives are to develop and pilot a PIVC placement policy and training program, pilot the PIVC insertion skills program over a two-month period, and evaluate and modify the PIVC insertion skills training program based on the project's results. This section will outline the study's design, sample, setting, and procedures. The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation was used as the foundation for the methods section. The implementation was completed between February 2021, and March 2021, as indicated on the project's timeline (see Appendix B).

Study Design

An EBP approach was used to meet the aims of the project. Pre- and post-data assessed the effects of the PIVC training program on RN PIVC insertion skills knowledge and post-intervention data assessed RN PIVC insertion competency.

Setting and Sample

This project was completed at a small home health organization in Orange County, California. The sample included all employed RNs within the home health organization between February 2021, and March 2021. Those excluded from the sample were RNs who choose not to participate in the trainings and who did not complete the knowledge assessments and skills evaluation.

Ethical Considerations

The approval of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Los Angeles was obtained before the implementation of the intervention (see Appendix B). The home health organization did not require IRB approval since it is a quality improvement project.

The data from RNs were not shared with the employer and did not jeopardize participant employment or evaluation. Data was collected through an online forum and paper handouts. All data were reviewed after the implementation ended. The participants provided informed consent.

Procedure

As indicated, the Stevens Star Model of Knowledge of Transformation guided this DNP project. Utilizing star points one through five within the project is discussed below.

Star Point 1: Discovery Research

This first stage identified appropriate literature regarding PIVCs and training. This literature was critiqued to determine if it was beneficial for the project's purpose and objectives.

Star Point 2: Evidence Summary

The second stage required the author to create a Table of Evidence, grade the evidence using Polit and Beck's (2008) levels of evidence, and then synthesize the information into a literature review.

Star Point 3: Translation to Guidelines

This third stage required the author to create a PIVC skills competency training program policy and procedures to institute within a home health organization. The policy required all RNs entering the home health organization to undergo the PIVC skills training program, and their PIVC skills competency evaluated. The procedures of the EBP PIVC skills training program included:

1. Developing a consent form for the participants
2. Obtaining online video training material using current EBP content
 - a. The online video training was no longer than 30 minutes
3. Obtaining an IV simulation arm and PIVC insertion supplies

4. Developing didactic material required for the in-person simulation portion of the training program based on EBP
5. Developing a survey to be used that will include nurse demographics (e.g., years' experience, academic degrees, and certifications) and the PIVC insertion knowledge questionnaire (Keleekai et al., 2016; see Appendix D)
 - a. The knowledge questionnaire is 14-items and has 22 potential points. It included fill in the blanks, placing items in the correct sequence, and multiple-choice items (Keleekai et al., 2016). Each item was scored between 0 – 4.5 points. Higher scores indicated more knowledge. A pilot test of this instrument was conducted with 22 RNs “to measure 2-day test/retest reliability ($r = 0.81$)” (Keleekai et al., 2016, p. 379). No other information related to the validity and reliability was available at the time this paper was created. Consent to use this tool was obtained from the creator (see Appendix C). The PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment was self-administered via a digital format to participants before the training and was provided to the participants using paper handouts after the training and competency evaluation.
6. Developing a paper and pencil version of the PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist to be used in the PIVC simulations (Schuster et al., 2016a)
 - a. The skills checklist contains 28-items, 52-points, and two columns to evaluate two insertion attempts. A step performed correctly was given a score of 1 while an uncompleted step was given a score of 0 (Schuster et al., 2016a). Items 1 – 4 were omitted from evaluation during the second insertion attempt (Schuster et al., 2016a). The greatest point total from the first insertion attempt is 28 and 24

points from the second insertion attempt (Schuster et al., 2016a). Higher scores indicated greater insertion skill. Three experts in vascular access examined the checklist for validity and eight trained raters assessed the checklist within a simulation utilizing 63 clinicians (Schuster et al., 2016a). The PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist holds an internal consistency of $\alpha = 0.84$, an “individual item intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) between rater and gold standard observations ranged from -0.01 to 1.00 and total score ICC was 0.99 (95% confidence interval, 0.99-0.99)” (Schuster et al., 2016a, p. 196). Consent for use within the project was provided by the instrument’s creator (see Appendix E). An example of the checklist is provided (see Appendix F). The author evaluated each participant using the PIVC skills checklist during the simulations.

7. Developing a post-evaluation survey to allow the participants to appraise the PIVC insertion skills training program
8. Obtaining the incentive products which included personalized pens and a \$50 gift card. The personalized pens were given to all RNs who completed the online video training portion. All participants were entered into a drawing to receive the \$50 gift card. The winner was announced via email after the intervention ended

Star Point 4: Practice Integration

In this fourth stage, the author (see Appendix B):

1. Obtained approval from the California State University, Los Angeles IRB to conduct the training program
2. Provided the owner of the home health company, the Director of Nursing (DON), the Assistant DON, and the employed RNs, information on the training program. The author

collaborated with the home health office staff to communicate the training program details, which included details of the incentives with the RNs via email. These emails were sent out prior to the implementation. Multiple emails, however, were sent during the intervention period to remind the RNs of the project details

3. The author implemented the EBP PIVC training program February and March 2021. The author did not have assistants to help with implementation
 - a. Obtained oral consent from the participants (see Appendix G). Consent was presented to the participants via a letter linked to the email which included the pre-intervention PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment and demographic form.
 - b. Provided the participants with a link to the demographic form and pre-intervention PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment (see Appendix D) via an online survey tool
 - c. After their completion of the demographic form and pre-intervention PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment, participants were immediately provided with an anonymous Qualtrics link to the online video training. The online video training lasted approximately 30 minutes and is located at <https://youtu.be/aXJZSYOh6dU>
 - d. Ensured completion of online video training before in-person simulation
 - e. Held multiple in-person simulation training days at the California Career Institute's simulation center
 - i. The in-person simulation training was no longer than one hour

- f. Provided the participants with the didactic training material using lecture and a PowerPoint presentation (see Appendix H). The lecture lasted roughly 20 minutes.
- g. Allowed participants to complete one successful PIVC insertion attempt with the PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist as a guide.
- h. Removed the participants' copies of the PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist and allowed the participants to attempt two PIVC insertions and evaluated the participant using the PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist.
- i. Participants completed a self-administered post-intervention PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment questionnaire (see Appendix D). The post-intervention knowledge questionnaire included the same questions as the pre-intervention knowledge questionnaire.
- j. Concluded implementation.

Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation

In this last stage, the author obtained, examined the data, evaluated the program, and created modifications to improve the program. First, the author analyzed demographic data using descriptive statistics including count, percentages, means, ranges, and standard deviations. Next, the author compared the participants' pre- and post-implementation knowledge questionnaires and the skills evaluation scores. Data from the pre- and post-PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment were analyzed by noting each nurse's pre- and post-intervention scores and documenting the count change. Furthermore, the author averaged the total count scores. Next, the author analyzed the data from the PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist with two approaches. First, the author listed each item of the checklist and reported the number and percentage of nurses

who completed each item of the checklist. The skills with the most and least frequencies were reported. Second, the author recorded each RN's score, in percentages, from each insertion attempt. The author then averaged the total scores. Lastly, the program was evaluated and modified based on the data analysis and the nurses' evaluation of the program. The EBP PIVC skills competency training program and PIVC policy and procedures are finally developed and are sustainable.

Results

Four data sets were analyzed: Demographics, PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores, RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items, and Percentage Completed of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist. The results examined three RNs within the home health organization. The participation rate of the study was 37.5% as three of eight RNs participated in the training. All three RNs completed the training thoroughly and as directed by the author.

RN Demographics

Three RNs completed the intervention. The mean years of nursing experience were 15.33 years, the range was from 4 to 30 years, and the standard deviation of the years was 10.873. One RN had a certification that was not IV related. The highest level of education was determined to be a master's degree which one RN held (see Table 1).

Table 1

Demographics

Years of Nursing Experience	Mean 15.33 (range 4-30, SD 10.873)
Certifications (number of nurses with any certification)	1 (33%)
Highest Level of Education	1 - Master's Degree (33%)

PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores

Of the three RNs who were studied, two RNs received lower PIVC insertion knowledge scores after the intervention. One RN's score did increase, however, post-intervention. The

minimum score was 10.5 and the maximum score was 19. Overall, the total count change score was 1 and the average count change score was 0.33 (see Table 2).

Table 2

PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores

Nurse	Pre-PIVC Knowledge Score	Post-PIVC Knowledge Score	Count Change
1	11	10.5	-0.5
2	12	14.5	2.5
3	19	18	-1
TOTAL COUNT CHANGE SCORE: 1			
AVERAGE COUNT CHANGE SCORE: 0.33			

RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items

The PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist included 28 items. Of the 28 items, fewer than 100% of the RNs completed three of the items. These three items were 9, 13, and 28. 67% of the RNs completed items 9, 13, and 28 (see Table 3). This percentage considered both insertion attempts, as the RNs were assessed twice. Item 9 was for the RN to choose a catheter appropriate for the therapy and vein (Schuster et al., 2016a), item 13 required the RN to caution the patient of the IV stick (Schuster et al., 2016a), and item 28 was for the RN to properly document the IV insertion (Schuster et al., 2016a). To ensure future RNs complete the checklist thoroughly; however, it is important for the training material to reference each item.

Table 3*RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items*

Checklist Item Skill	Number/ (%) of RNs Who Completed Skill Without Checklist Reference [includes both attempts]
1: Verify physician order	3 (100%)
2: Wash hands prior to patient contact	3 (100%)
3: Identify patient	3 (100%)
4: Explain purpose and procedure to the patient	3 (100%)
5: Dons gloves prior to procedure	3 (100%)
6: Apply tourniquet for vein assessment	3 (100%)
7: Assess, palpate and select suitable vein for access	3 (100%)
8: Gather & prepare all required equipment	3 (100%)
9: Select IV catheter suitable for vein & therapy	2 (67%)
10: Cleanse insertion site and allow to air dry	3 (100%)
11: Tourniquet on prior to insertion	3 (100%)
12: Perform vein traction, skin tension below insertion site with non-dominant hand	3 (100%)
13: Warn patient of stick	2 (67%)
14: Insert catheter with needle bevel up, at an appropriate angle	3 (100%)
15: Observe flash of blood in flashback chamber	3 (100%)
16: Lower the catheter parallel to the skin and advance the needle and catheter together 1/8 inch	3 (100%)
17: Advance the catheter off needle/stylet and thread into the vein	3 (100%)
18: Release tourniquet	3 (100%)
19: Compress vein distal to catheter tip & stabilize catheter hub to prevent dislodgement	3 (100%)
20: Remove the needle/stylet from the catheter and ensure safety mechanism is engaged	3 (100%)
21: Attach extension set with needleless connector	3 (100%)
22: Disinfect needleless connector per protocol	3 (100%)
23: Assess for patency, flush and lock	3 (100%)
24: Dispose of sharps in sharps container	3 (100%)
25: Dress and secure IV access site per hospital protocol	3 (100%)
26: Label dressing with date and initials	3 (100%)
27: Assess site and patient tolerance of procedure	3 (100%)
28: Document IV insertion correctly	2 (67%)

Percentage of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Completed

The RNs were evaluated with two PIVC insertion attempts without using the checklist as a reference. Completing items within the checklist increased their scores and their total percentages. Two RNs increased their percentages with their second insertion attempt, and one RN's percentage decreased with the second attempt (see Table 4). The total percent change score was 32% with the second PIVC attempt, and the average percent change score was 10.67.

Table 4

Percentage of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Completed

Nurse	Attempt 1 – % Completed	Attempt 2 – % Completed	% Change
1	61%	83%	22%
2	86%	100%	14%
3	100%	96%	-4%
TOTAL % CHANGE SCORE: 32%			
AVERAGE % CHANGE SCORE: +10.67			

Discussion

The purpose of this DNP project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a PIVC insertion training program for home health infusion RNs within an organization in Orange County, CA. The objectives were to develop and pilot a PIVC placement policy and training program, pilot the PIVC skills program over two months, and evaluate and modify the PIVC program based on project results. Both the purpose and the objectives were achieved.

The policy and training program will be instituted within the home health organization for newly hired RNs to complete during their orientation. The policy addressed elements such as IV placement, safety, and infection control (see Appendix I). The online video and hands-on training portion were developed using current, scientific knowledge, and previous studies provided the PIVC assessments. The implementation occurred over months, and the training program was evaluated and modified based on the results. The final program was based on questions and concerns brought by the RNs during the intervention; emphasized information found within the PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment and the PIVC Skills Checklist; and lastly, incorporated longer in-person training time.

This DNP project identified the need for more research regarding PIVC training programs for RNs within home health organizations. As the home health organization studied did not include formal PIVC training and a PIVC competency checklist prior to the author's implementation of the training program, RNs were shown to benefit from the PIVC training program which utilized both online video and hands-on portions. Overall, the data detailed that PIVC insertion competency improved as PIVC insertion knowledge and skills increased with training and practice.

Some unexpected findings did occur, however. Although the overall data showed that training improved RNs' competency; one RN's scores decreased on the post-implementation assessment score and the second PIVC insertion attempt, while noting feeling an increase of nervousness when completing these tasks in front of a colleague. Furthermore, another RN's knowledge assessment scores were comparably low as this RN stated a history of hesitancy with starting PIVCs. Other factors that might contribute to these unexpected findings are nursing experience and level of education. The average years of nursing experience was 15 years and the highest level of education an RN obtained was a Master of Science in Nursing. This developed training program, however, targeted newly hired RNs who may have limited PIVC competence and experience, and may have not acquired higher levels of nursing education.

Limitations

Limitations within the study were prevalent. The DNP project was conducted within one home health organization that is small and employs eight RNs. Though all RNs were notified of the PIVC training program, only three RNs expressed interest. With a limited number of RNs within the population and sample, it was challenging to obtain a more significant percentage of participants and led to sampling and membership biases. Furthermore, the project took place over two months. Should implementation have taken place over a longer period, the opportunity of garnering more participation may have been possible, thus, expanding the amount of potential data collection. Lastly, as the COVID-19 pandemic continues to affect everyday life, it is understandable to opt-out of conducting more undertakings than are required, as being involved with the project could place one at risk of contracting or spreading the virus. Management did not require all current RNs to participate in the PIVC training.

Future Implications

This project's implementation suggested the importance of increasing research concerning home health RNs and PIVC training programs as there are insufficient studies. The results also indicated that PIVC training programs are beneficial to home health RNs. Although the sample size was small, the overall results confirmed PIVC training programs benefit home health RNs. Implementing this study among a larger sample size would also provide valuable data.

Improvements to the training program could be to increase hands-on practice time and include more information into the training portions related to the PIVC knowledge assessment. Furthermore, as this DNP project accepted assistance from the California Career Institute to utilize their simulation center and supplies, it would also be feasible for home health companies to invest in simulation PIVC supplies and simulation arms to conduct PIVC training.

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APPENDIX A

Consent to Use the Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

Titan Apps

Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

ACE Star Model

Stevens, Kathleen R <[REDACTED]>
 To: Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

Wed, Mar 18, 2020 at 7:29 AM

Greetings, Hazel...

I am pleased that you find the Stevens Star Model helpful...and that you wish to use it in your scholarly work.

This email can serve as my confirmation of permission for your using the Model in your project.

I am happy to provide permission to you to use/reproduce the Star Model under the fair-use rule for educational uses, with the stipulation that credit is cited, as you indicated. This includes publication of materials on your university site. If later, you are re-publishing the copyrighted material (as in publishing in a journal or book), specific permission is required by the publisher. In that case, there is usually a template letter of permission from the publisher that I will readily sign.

Note the official name of the model in the PPT... the Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation copyright 2015.

I have attached an image that you may use, indicating my expressed permission.

Because I am tracking the uptake and spread of the Model, I am requesting a few items:

Kindly provide the name of your supervising professor and a brief description of how the Model applies to your project.

The interconnected "suite" of EBP materials I developed have served well a number of projects:

1. The Model is attached...it is the core of understanding "knowledge transformation"; details can be organized around each point of the star.
2. The national consensus on Essential EBP Competencies (2005 and 2009) used the Model provides as the conceptual framework.
3. In turn, the competencies set the stage for the EBP Readiness Inventory...a self-efficacy instrument, shown to have strong psychometrics; currently being used by others in multiples studies.

See these articles for discussion and use of these 3 resources:

•Stevens, KR. (2013). The impact of evidence-based practice in nursing and the next big ideas. Online Journal of Nursing Issues. 8 (2), 4. (open access) THIS IS THE ONE YOU HAVE ALREADY LOCATED <http://www.nursingworld.org/MainMenuCategories/ANAMarketplace/ANAPeriodicals/OJIN/TableofContents/Vol-18-2013/No2-May-2013/Impact-of-Evidence-Based-Practice.html>

•Saunders, H., Stevens, K. R., & Vehviläinen-Julkunen, K. (2016). Nurses' readiness for evidence-based practice at Finnish university hospitals: a national survey. Journal of advanced nursing. 29 MAR 2016. doi: 10.1111/jan.12963

While my web site is being revamped, some other materials are not currently available...however, here are a couple of videos that may be of interest:

YouTube:

- Interview done by Boston Childrens Hospital... 38 minute interview from OpenPediatrics July 2019, entitled, *The Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation to Improve Care and Outcomes*, available at <https://www.openpediatrics.org/assets/video/stevens-star-model-knowledge-transformation-improve-care-and-outcomes>
- Part of my Schools 50th Anniversary Celebration and published January 2020, entitled, *Translational Science*. In this 13-minute video I connect EBP to what I consider the next stage in evolution (translational science, particularly implementation research) to transform healthcare and population health; available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A3KXzSXegVM>

Would be interested in hearing what other resources would be helpful...

Congratulations on your career goals!

Thank you for your efforts in improving care, safety, and patient outcomes.

And thank you for the well-wishes...indeed, we will all be shaped by current events. And most likely, many benefits will derive from our repositioning 'everything.'

Be well, be patient, be kind.

DrS

...to the best of our knowledge

Dr. Kathleen R. Stevens, RN, EdD, ANEF, FAAN

[Quoted text hidden]

 AAA Star Model Single PPT (2).pptx
56K

APPENDIX B

Project Timeline

DATE	ACTIVITIES
APRIL 2020	Obtained permission to utilize the knowledge assessment and skills checklist
MAY 2020	Submitted project proposal to California State University, Los Angeles IRB
SUMMER 2020	Obtained online video training material Created didactic training material
NOVEMBER 2020	Obtained approval to utilize the California Career Institute's simulation center, peripheral IV supplies and simulation arm
JANUARY 2021	Received project approval from IRB
FEBRUARY 2021	Informed RNs of project Implemented intervention
MARCH 2021	Completed intervention Analyzed data
	Evaluated/Modified intervention

APPENDIX C

Consent to Use the PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Tool

Titan Apps

Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Research

Keleekai-Brapoh, Nowai <[REDACTED]>

Thu, Apr 23, 2020 at 8:08 AM

To: Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

Hi Hazel,

[REDACTED]

The simulation tools that we are utilizing for PIVC training at our organization presently are:

- VATA boards – Nasco Life Form
- Mannikin Arms – Armstrong Medical

I have attached the PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment tool and answer key that you are free to use, with proper citations. Should you modify, please note accordingly in any dissemination.

Best of luck and hope that you are well through all of this!

Nowai Keleekai-Brapoh, PhD, RN, NPD-BC

Nurse Researcher

[REDACTED]

APPENDIX D

PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Tool

PIVC SBML Research Knowledge Assessment

Study PIN #: _____ Date: _____

1. Identify the veins on the following images by writing the name of the vein in each of the blanks provided, select from the list of vein names below.

- | | |
|----------------------|----------------------|
| ● Metacarpal | ● Digital |
| ● Dorsal venous arch | ● Cephalic |
| ● Median | ● Ancillary Cephalic |
| ● Basilic | |

Study Time point 1 2 3 4 5 ****For Observer Use Only**** Initials _____

APPENDIX E

Consent to Use the Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Skills Checklist

Titan Apps

Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Skills Checklist

Catherine Schuster <[REDACTED]>
To: Hazel Danggoec <hdanggoec@csu.fullerton.edu>

Thu, Apr 30, 2020 at 2:07 PM

Hi Hazel
[REDACTED]

Yes you have my permission to use the checklist...just cite appropriately.

[REDACTED] Best of luck with your project!

Stay healthy and happy!

Catherine Schuster, PhD, RN
Sent from Yahoo Mail for iPhone

[Quoted text hidden]

APPENDIX F

Peripheral IV Catheter Insertion Skills Checklist

Study Pin # _____

Peripheral IV Catheter (PIVC) Insertion Skills Checklist

1. Verify physician order	<input type="checkbox"/>	--
2. Wash hands prior to patient contact	<input type="checkbox"/>	--
3. Identify patient	<input type="checkbox"/>	--
4. Explain purpose and procedure to the patient	<input type="checkbox"/>	--
5. Dons gloves prior to procedure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Apply tourniquet for vein assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Assess, palpate and select suitable vein for access	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Gather & prepare all required equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Select IV catheter suitable for vein & therapy (gauge & length)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10. Cleanse insertion site and allow to air dry (per protocol)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11. Tourniquet on prior to insertion (at least 4-6 inches above insertion site)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12. Perform vein traction, skin tension below insertion site with non-dominant hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13. Warn patient of stick	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14. Insert catheter with needle bevel up, at an appropriate angle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15. Observe flash of blood in flashback chamber	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16. Lower the catheter parallel to the skin and advance the needle and catheter together 1/8 inch	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17. Advance the catheter off needle/stylet and thread into the vein	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18. Release tourniquet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

APPENDIX G

Participant Consent Form Letter

[Improving Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Insertion Competency of Home Health Nurses]

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by [Hazel Mary Danggoec, a DNP student at the California State University Southern California DNP Consortium]. In this study we hope to learn more about [home health RNs]. You were selected to participate in this study [through voluntary participation as you are an RN employed with ██████████]. We hope that our research will lead to [improving peripheral intravenous catheter insertion skills and knowledge]. [Participants will be provided educational material and will have the ability to practice establishing peripheral intravenous catheter insertion on a simulation arm.]

[The subject will be assessed on their peripheral intravenous catheter insertion knowledge and skill. The subject will be given educational material. Lastly, the subject will also practice their peripheral intravenous catheter insertion skill on a simulation arm. The online portion of the training will be approximately 30 minutes and the hands-on training portion will be approximately 1 hour. The participants who complete the online training will be provided a personalized pen and the participants who complete both the online training and hands-on training will be entered into a drawing for a \$50 Amazon gift card. Per the requirements of California gambling law, you may participate in the drawing even if you do not complete or participate in the study by asking the investigator to include you.]

[There are minimal risks to participating in this study. Risks of the study include possible discomfort when being assessed for peripheral intravenous catheter insertion knowledge and skill, risk of the loss of confidentiality, and potential risk of needle sticks as subjects who participate in the hands-on training will be asked to insert peripheral intravenous catheters into a simulation arm. We do not expect any adverse medical effects to occur. In the event of an injury or illness as the result of participation in this research project, the subject may seek basic medical and/or mental health care through a personal/outside health care provider for care and treatment. In all cases, in the event of need for emergency medical care, 911 will be called. Any and all incurred health care costs associated with participation in this research project are the responsibility of the subject.]

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you choose to participate, we will protect your confidentiality. [Files will be stored within a locked box throughout the study and will be kept with the co-investigator. The files will then be stored within the office of ██████████ after the completion of the study for a minimum of three years. Files within the locked box will not contain any personal identifiers. Qualtrics data will also be stored for a minimum of three years and investigators will be the only persons able to access the data.]

[We approximate 4 participants].

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call [Dr. Ayman Tailakh] at ██████████ or write [him] at ██████████. [Hazel Mary Danggoec, Co-Investigator, at ██████████ or ██████████]

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

APPENDIX H**Didactic Training Material**

Peripheral Intravenous (IV) Insertion Training

APPENDIX I

Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Placement Policy

Peripheral Intravenous Catheter (PIVC) Insertion for Home Health Registered Nurses (RNs)

Purpose

To ensure Registered Nurses (RNs) safe insertion of a peripheral intravenous catheter (PIVC) within a home health setting.

Policy

Intravenous catheter insertions will be inserted by RNs. RNs who perform PIVC insertions may do so only under the following conditions:

1. Must undergo and pass PIVC training during new-hire orientation
2. Will have PIVC competency assessed annually
3. RN will be given 2 PIVC insertion attempts when with a patient
 - a. Should RN unsuccessfully insert a PIVC within 2 attempts, RN will contact office to either send an assisting RN to establish a PIVC or contact the physician to establish a peripherally inserted central catheter (PICC) line
 - i. The Director of Nursing (DON) will determine if RN is in need of more PIVC insertion training if the patient is considered to be an "easy stick" patient

Procedure

1. Verify provider order and determine need for PIVC.
2. Wash hands
3. Explain purpose and procedure to patient
4. Acquire PIVC insertion equipment
 - a. Choose appropriate IV catheter suitable for therapy